

Vol 42 (4) December, 2018

Print: ISSN 0304 4904
Online: ISSN 2305-820X

PAKISTAN PEDIATRIC JOURNAL

A JOURNAL OF PAKISTAN PEDIATRIC ASSOCIATION

Indexed in EMBASE/Excerpta Medica, Index Medicus WHO
IMEMR & Global Health/CAB Abstracts

www.pakpedsjournal.org.pk

<http://www.pakmedinet.com/PPJ>

ORIGINAL ARTICLE

Awareness and Knowledge about Autism Spectrum Disorder among Mainstream and Special School Teachers in Lahore

ZARA FAROOQ, NAZISH IMRAN, SHEHARYAR WARRAICH, Ali Shehbaz Baloch, Ruhma Hussain

Pak Pediatr J 2018; 42(4): 247-54

ABSTRACT

Background: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) affects a significant number of school going children. Awareness among teachers plays a major role in its early identification.

Objective: To assess and compare the knowledge and awareness about ASD among mainstream and special school teachers of Lahore.

Methods: 163 teachers (99 mainstream, 64 special school) were recruited by purposive sampling. A cross-sectional survey was conducted and descriptive analysis was run on the whole data.

Results: Though knowledge about ASD was poor overall, special school teachers were better informed. Females were predominantly (n=155) represented in the sample. 64.4 % respondents were aware that early intervention was significant, only 35% believed in teaching Autistic children in mainstream schools, 90.8% agreed with the need to train teachers.

Conclusion: The lack of sufficient knowledge about ASD among school teachers necessitates training them about developmental disorders to make early recognition and management of potential cases of ASD possible.

Key-words: Autism Spectrum Disorder, Knowledge, Teachers, Special schools.

Correspondence to:

Zara Farooq,
King Edward Medical University,
Lahore, Pakistan

E-mail: zarafarooq18@gmail.com

Received 17th August 2018;
Accepted for publication
11th October 2018

INTRODUCTION

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a pervasive neurodevelopmental disorder, characterized by social impairment, communication deficits (verbal and non-verbal), and repetitive and restricted behavioral patterns and interests¹. According to the changes made in DSM-5, individuals with a well-established DSM-IV diagnosis of Autistic disorder, Asperger's disorder, Childhood Disintegrative Disorder or Pervasive Developmental Disorder not Otherwise Specified

should be given the diagnosis of Autism Spectrum Disorder². Symptoms of Autism Spectrum Disorder are highly variable. They can range from severe functional impairment to a mild delay, and manifest mostly within first two-and-a-half years of life. The appearance of children with Autism Spectrum Disorder is normal but their behavior is puzzling and markedly different from normal children³. Autism is an idiopathic disorder^{4,5}; its cause can be attributed to a genetic basis^{6,7}, influenced by certain risk factors including male gender (male: female ratio is 3-4:1), family history,

age of parents, disorders such as fragile X syndrome, tuberous sclerosis, Tourette's syndrome and epilepsy⁸ and drugs used during pregnancy⁹. Autism is thought of as a spectral disorder⁴. Symptoms of autism are highly heterogeneous¹⁰.

The incidence of autism has steadily increased over the past decade; it is now estimated to be 1-2%¹¹. Autism affects a significant number of school going children. The behavior and learning abilities of children with Autism are different from other children and teachers to be need to be equipped with the requisite skills to deal with them¹². Limited research exists regarding the role of teachers in screening for Autism Spectrum Disorder¹³. Despite advancements in instructional practices for students with Autism, little attention has been given to examining the qualities of special and general education teachers who deliver services to these students in inclusive settings¹⁴. According to Pakistan's Country Report for Autism, 1 in every 120 children is suffering from autism¹⁵. The reported incidence is much lower than the actual one mainly due to lack of awareness¹⁶ about autism among physicians, psychologists, psychiatrists and speech therapists leading to under-diagnosis. In Pakistan a certain amount of reluctance is seen in labelling the child as 'autistic.' With the increasing incidence of autism, every public and private school is likely to serve children with Autism. Woefully, many teachers in sub-continent^{17,18} lack the knowledge, awareness and understanding about Autism to cater to the needs of these special children.

Teachers interact with their students on a daily basis. Many of the signs and symptoms of autism manifest themselves in a classroom setting and since early intervention is paramount in managing children with Autism, knowledge about Autism Spectrum Disorder among school teachers is of utmost importance for recognizing those signs.

The present study is aimed to assess and compare the knowledge and awareness regarding Autism Spectrum Disorders among mainstream and special school teachers in Lahore. This comparison would serve as a guideline for future models to train teachers regarding the special needs of children with Autism.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

It was a cross sectional study conducted at

selected mainstream (primary) and special schools in Lahore. After approval from Institutional Review Board of King Edward Medical University, 10 special schools and 3 mainstream schools in Lahore were contacted to obtain permission for data collection from their administrations. Only primary school teachers were contacted. 181 teachers were recruited from the schools. Following written informed consent, data was collected through a self-administered questionnaire. The questionnaire was piloted among 15 school teachers (who were not part of the study sample) prior to study to get their feedback on the wording and content of the questionnaire. Minor changes were made based on their feedback.

The questionnaire was based on previous literature on this topic^{17,19} and was designed to assess various aspects of symptoms, etiology, diagnosis and treatment. It had two sections: the first section collected information on key demographic variables (age, gender, qualification, school type, and experience) and questions about any previous knowledge about Autism Spectrum Disorder and its source(s). The second section consisted on 21 questions (with the first question having 11 parts) assessing knowledge about signs and symptoms, associated features, causative factors, diagnostic criteria and treatment of Autism Spectrum Disorder. This part of the questionnaire was viewed and verified by a child psychiatrist and psychologist and the Cronbach's alpha for this section was calculated to be 0.89. The questions in the 2nd section were Yes/No questions with a 'Don't Know' option included. Participants were also asked about the necessity of holding a training session for teachers on ASD and their willingness to attend it. Data was analyzed using SPSS version 20. The 21 questions gauging knowledge and awareness about ASD in section 2 were scored with every correct answer coded with a score of 1, and every incorrect and 'Don't Know' answer coded with a score of 0. Chi square test was used to compare differences in knowledge and attitudes among mainstream and special school teachers. Descriptive statistics were run on the whole data and P value <0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

Among the 181 questionnaires distributed, 165

questionnaires were returned. Two forms were excluded due to incomplete data entry and the final sample size amounted to 163. Ninety-nine respondents were from mainstream schools and sixty-four were from special schools. The mean age of the participants was 35.04 years (SD 9.26) years. Female predominance (n=155) was observed with the number of male respondents being only 8. Gender, therefore, was excluded as a variable. 65% of the teachers had more than five years of teaching experience with mean teaching experience being 2.55 years (SD 0.66 years).

Qualifications of the teachers were varied. 70% had a master's degree, 25.8% respondents had a bachelor's degree, 4.9% had a diploma in speech therapy and only 0.6% had diploma in physiotherapy and physical education each. 25.2% respondents had technical education in Bachelor of Education (B.Ed.) and 12.5% had completed Master of Education (M.Ed.)

77.9% (n=127) respondents mentioned having heard about or having prior knowledge about ASD. Sources of were varied, as shown by fig-1, with books being the most common source.

The 2nd part of the questionnaire had 21 questions (with the first question having 11 parts) assessing the knowledge and awareness about Autism Spectrum Disorder. Cronbach's alpha for this section of the questionnaire was 0.89. Table 1

shows the number and percentage of correct answers for these 31 items for mainstream school teachers, special school teachers and the entire study sample.

Fig-1: Sources of Prior Knowledge about ASD

TABLE-1: Number and Percentage of Correct Answers

Question	General Schools (99)		Special Schools (64)		Total(163)		P-value
	Correct Answer		Correct Answer		Correct Answer		
	N	%	N	%	N	%	
What do you think a child with Autism would do/has							
a) Look at other children when interacting with them or make good eye contact.	39	39.4	42	65.6	81	49.7	0.003*
b) Language development is delayed.	71	71.7	61	95.3	132	81	0.001*
c) No perception of fear or danger e.g.: crosses road without looking.	36	36.4	7	10.9	43	26.5	0.000**
d) Upset at even minor changes in routine, obsessed with the same routine.	73	73.7	59	92.2	132	81.1	0.009*

e)	Make good and appropriate use of hand and body gestures when having conversations.	52	52.5	43	67.2	95	58.3	0.097
f)	Has intellectual disability.	31	31.3	37	57.8	68	41.7	0.000**
g)	Has repetitive behavior (flapping hands, body rocking repeatedly).	69	69.7	59	92.2	128	78.5	0.003*
h)	Does not respond to name.	37	37.4	46	71.9	83	50.9	0.000**
i)	Does not respond to emotional cues, i.e. to affection. Does not like to be cuddled or hugged	33	33.3	45	70.3	78	47.9	0.000**
j)	Inappropriate attachment to certain toys or objects (prefers to play with same toy for hours)	62	62.6	61	65.3	123	75.5	0.000**
k)	Fails to show interest in other children or no interest in interacting with other children.	62	62.6	55	85.9	117	72.2	0.003*
	Children with Autism tend to be auditory learners.	20	20.2	21	32.8	41	25.2	0.166
	Some children with Autism manifest special abilities like drawing and facts and figures remembering	84	84.8	54	84.4	138	84.7	0.764
	Autism is usually diagnosed during the first three years of child's age.	57	57.6	49	76.6	106	65	0.000**
	Autism is associated with epilepsy.	21	21.2	18	28.1	39	23.9	0.000**
	Some children have high or low sensitivity of visual, auditory, tactile or olfactory stimuli.	77	77.8	58	90.6	135	82.8	0.057
	Autism is a life-long condition.	32	32.3	54	84.4	86	52.8	0.000**
	Autism can be diagnosed through behavioral observation	84	84.8	56	87.5	140	85.9	0.397
	Genetic factors is a cause of Autism.	53	53.5	33	51.6	86	52.8	0.488
	Autism can be diagnosed through physical features	29	29.3	41	64.1	70	42.9	0.000**
	Poor parenting skills can cause ASD	27	27.3	39	60.9	66	40.5	0.000**
	In many cases, cause of Autism is unknown	64	64.6	53	82.8	117	71.8	0.005*
	Autism is a developmental disorder.	58	58.6	35	59.4	96	58.9	0.169
	Medicines can improve core symptoms of Autism.	18	18.2	33	51.6	51	31.3	0.000**
	Early intervention improves prognosis.	51	51.5	54	84.4	105	64.4	0.000**
	Majority of children with autism are female.	40	40.4	47	73.4	87	53.4	0.000**
	Speech therapy helps in alleviating symptoms of Autism.	71	71.7	39	60.9	110	67.5	0.000**
	Autism is a rare condition in our country as compared to the West.	19	19.2	25	39.1	44	27.1	0.003*
	Poor parenting practices can cause Autism.	32	32.3	38	59.4	70	42.9	0.002*
	Children with Autism prefer routine activities	35	35.4	12	18.8	47	28.8	0.000**
	Children with Autism should be taught in Special schools.	26	26.3	9	14.1	35	21.5	0.052

*p-value: <0.05

**p-value: <0.001

As shown in table 1, special school teachers knowledge about signs and symptoms of ASD achieved statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) over mainstream school teachers. However, interestingly, mainstream school teachers had statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) better knowledge about the lack of perception of fear and danger in children with Autism than special school teachers.

Special school teacher's knowledge about causative factors of ASD reached statistical significance over ($p < 0.05$) mainstream school teachers (table-1). 71.8 % showed accurate knowledge about the cause of ASD not bring known yet. 52.8% respondents were aware of ASD being a life-long condition. Only 40.5 % of the respondents knew that poor parenting practices do not cause ASD. Knowledge about genetics as a cause of ASD and it being a development disorder was poor in both groups

Special school teachers had significantly ($p < 0.001$) better knowledge about ASD not manifesting as physical features and it being diagnosed in the first 3 years of life. 85.9% of the teachers knew that Autism can be diagnosed through behavioral observation.

Though both mainstream and special school teachers had an overall poor knowledge about associated features of ASD, special school teachers knowledge showed statistical significance in a few questions related to associated features. Mainstream teachers, however, showed a significantly ($p < 0.001$) better knowledge about children with Autism not preferring normal routine activities. 53.4% of the respondents were aware that ASD is more common in males. Only 25.2% of the participants knew that children with Autism are not auditory learners, only 23.9% knew of its association with epilepsy and only 27.1 % knew that ASD is in fact not rare in our country as compared to the West but merely underdiagnosed.

Special school teachers showed a statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) better knowledge than mainstream school teachers about how early intervention improves symptoms of ASD and lack of the ability of medicines to improve core symptoms of Autism. Overall, while 64.4 % of the respondents knew that early intervention can improve core symptoms, only 31.3 % were aware

that medicines do not play a significant role in treating symptoms of ASD. Though both groups had a good knowledge about the positive impact of speech therapy in alleviating symptoms of ASD, mainstream school teachers had significantly ($p < 0.001$) better knowledge about this.

Only 26.3% of mainstream school teachers and 14.1% of special school teachers believed that children with autism should be taught in mainstream schools.

The mean score of mainstream and special school teachers, based on the number of correct responses, was calculated, as shown in table-2.

TABLE 2: Comparison of Mean Scores

School	Questionnaire score (Maximum score possible was 31) Mean (SD)	P. value
Mainstream schools	14.78(4.7)	.000**
Special schools	20.0(3.4)	

**P-value $< .001$

There was significant difference ($P < 0.001$) between the average score of mainstream and special school teachers in question about knowledge and awareness about Autism Spectrum Disorder. This comparative score shows that special school teachers have a better knowledge about ASD as compared to mainstream school teachers.

Teachers were asked about the need for training teachers on Autism and their willingness to attend the training session. 90.8% ($n=148$) of the respondents agreed that there is a need to train teachers with 76.1% ($n=124$) of the respondents willing to attend the session.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this study was to assess and compare the knowledge and awareness regarding Autism Spectrum Disorders among mainstream and special school teachers in Lahore. It specifically aimed to assess knowledge about signs and symptoms, causal factors, diagnosis and treatment of ASD and if the type of school affected level of knowledge. Study revealed poor knowledge among both, with special school teachers having a significantly better knowledge

than mainstream teachers. This may be due to lack of proper training of teachers after conclusion of their studies and limited number of workshops available, especially on special needs children. Lack of interaction of mainstream school teachers with children with Autism Spectrum Disorder may also be a major factor contributing to their low knowledge. As derived from "contact hypothesis"²⁰ there is literature that suggest that having previous contact with a disabled person erodes negative view. This is based on the assumption that when one side is exposed to the other; new understanding emerges and prejudice weakens. Other factors contributing to low level of knowledge may be the taboo associated with mental disorders in the sub-continent. A study about lay-beliefs about autism showed that individual difference among factors such as religiousness, interest in mental illness, age and knowledge of autism predicted beliefs²¹. Teachers may also fear backlash from parents if they attribute any unusual behavior of the child with a developmental disorder, leading to low rates of reporting. A study conducted in Finland reported rare agreement between parents and teachers asked to fill Autism Spectrum Screening Questionnaire²².

The results of this study are similar to the results of a study conducted in Saudi Arabia¹⁹ comparing mainstream and special school teachers' knowledge about ASD. The study indicated that school teachers had an acceptable approaching to weak level of knowledge about Autism disorder with significant differences in the teachers' knowledge about Autism favoring special education teachers. Study conducted in Karachi¹⁸ comparing knowledge about ASD among public and private mainstream school teachers concluded that there was a lack of awareness regarding autism among teachers from both the sectors, yet public schools' teachers were better aware. The lack of awareness is not limited to school teachers. A survey of Autism knowledge and attitudes among the healthcare professionals in Lahore, Pakistan¹⁶ found that professional had an unbalanced understanding of autism due to presence of several misconceptions regarding many of the salient features of autism. A study conducted in Istanbul²³ about pharmacists' awareness, knowledge and attitude about childhood autism found their knowledge was

lacking and that they tend to believe in outdated theories. Low level of knowledge about ASD among health care professionals, teachers and religious leaders causes families with a child with ASD considerable economic and emotional burden, as revealed by a study done in Goa²⁴.

Due to lack of formal training programs in sub-continent about childhood psychiatric illnesses, the source of knowledge about ASD is usually books and media, as revealed by our study and the studies done in India¹⁷ and Karachi¹⁸. The flawed portrayal about ASD leads often leads to misconception about ASD. This is supported by study done in Oman²⁵, which reveals that the severe misconception among teachers about ASD is likely due to sociocultural patterning and the conflicting views created by the scientific community and mass media. Even though aloof, rejecting parenting are no longer considered an etiology of ASD, as proved by researchers in the field²⁶, many teachers in our study believed that poor parenting practices result in ASD. This view about the role of parents is shared by respondents in studies done in Saudi Arabia¹⁹ and Oman²⁵ about knowledge of ASD among teachers. Misconception was also observed among our responders in thinking that medicines improve the core symptoms of ASD. A systemic review²⁷ of medications commonly used to treat autism revealed lack of evidence of effectiveness of these treatments.

Just like our study, a research done in Greece²⁸ to examine perceptions about autism in regular education and special education revealed that special education teachers were more likely to identify correctly the specific characteristics of autism. Through proper training of teachers we can greatly improve the quality of education of autistic children and improve their intellectual ability, as observed in in British Columbia²⁹, where a resource book was published by the Ministry of Education and multiple tools were given to help teachers when facing Autistic children. A few of the children also started attending a normal school later. It was observed that over 76 % of our respondents were actually willing to attend training sessions and workshops to better learn about ASD. The arrangement of such sessions is thus the need of the hour.

There are a number of limitations to this study. This is a cross-sectional study with a relatively small sample size which may have affected the generalizability of the findings. Data was collected based on convenience sampling by only those schools who agreed to take part in the research though efforts were made to make the data representative of all school settings common in Pakistan by collecting data from private, government and army run special and mainstream schools. Sample size was not calculated because of it being a small scale, time limited project but it should be considered in any future studies. The data was collected from schools in urban areas only. Moreover, the data was collected from Lahore, a provincial capital, where the level of awareness and knowledge may be different from peripheries. Another limitation is that teachers may have chosen the perceived favorable answer to hide lack of awareness. Since the teachers were asked to choose between 'Yes', 'No' and 'don't know' options instead of listing what they knew about ASD, choice of the correct option by chance may have led to overestimation of correct answers. It, however, is one of the first study of its kind conducted in Pakistan comparing the knowledge and awareness about ASD among special and mainstream school teachers with representative data from private, government and army run schools.

In conclusion, the results suggest that there is lack of sufficient knowledge and awareness about ASD among both special and mainstream school teachers. Special school teachers, however, a significantly better knowledge and awareness than mainstream school teachers about the signs and symptoms of ASD, its causal factors, diagnostic features and criteria and treatment options. Steps need to be taken to improve the knowledge of teachers, especially those teaching in mainstream schools, about ASD and other childhood developmental disorders through workshops, lectures and courses as it may lead to both an early recognition of potential cases of ASD as well as make inclusion of children with Autism in mainstream schools and catering to their needs easier.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to acknowledge Muhammad

Mohsin Ali, Final Year student of King Edward Medical University for his invaluable help with initial study design, questionnaire formation and data collection.

We would also like to acknowledge Fatima Baluch, also a Final Year student of King Edward Medical University for her help with the review of the relevant literature and manuscript writing.

Author's affiliations

Zara Farooq, Sheharyar Warraich, Ali Shehbaz Baluch, Ruhma Hussain

King Edward Medical University, Lahore, Pakistan

Nazish Imran,

Child & Family Psychiatry, King Edward Medical University/Mayo Hospital, Lahore, Pakistan

REFERENCES

1. American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders-IV-TR. Washington, DC: American Psychiatric Association. 2000.
2. American Psychiatric Association. Diagnostic and statistical manual of mental disorders (DSM-5®). American Psychiatric Pub; 2013 May 22.
3. Is it Autism? [Internet]. Autism Research Institute. Available from: https://www.autism.com/is_it_autism
4. Autism Spectrum Disorder [Internet]. Medline Plus. Available from: <https://medlineplus.gov/autismspectrumdisorder.html>
5. Newschaffer CJ, Croen LA, Daniels J, Giarelli E, Grether JK, Levy SE, Mandell DS, Miller LA, Pinto-Martin J, Reaven J, Reynolds AM. The epidemiology of autism spectrum disorders. *Annu. Rev. Public Health.* 2007 Apr 21;28:235-58.
6. Abrahams BS, Geschwind DH. Advances in autism genetics: on the threshold of a new neurobiology. *Nature reviews genetics.* 2008 May;9(5):341.
7. Muhle R, Trentacoste SV, Rapin I. The genetics of autism. *Pediatrics.* 2004 May 1;113(5):e472-86.
8. Autism spectrum disorder [Internet]. Mayo Clinic. 2018. Available from: <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/autism-spectrum-disorder/symptoms-causes/syc-20352928>

9. Williams G, King J, Cunningham M, Stephan M, Kerr B, Hersh JH. Fetal valproate syndrome and autism: additional evidence of an association. *Developmental Medicine & Child Neurology*. 2001 Mar 1;43(3):202-6
10. Mesibov GB, Shea V. Full inclusion and students with autism. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*. 1996 Jun 1;26(3):337-46.
11. Baio J. Prevalence of Autism Spectrum Disorders: Autism and Developmental Disabilities Monitoring Network, 14 Sites, United States, 2008. *Morbidity and Mortality Weekly Report. Surveillance Summaries*. Volume 61, Number 3. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention. 2012 Mar 30.
12. Simpson RL. Evidence-based practices and students with autism spectrum disorders. *Focus on Autism and Other Developmental Disabilities*. 2005 Aug 1;20(3):140-9.
13. Schanding GT, Nowell KP, Goin-Kochel RP. Utility of the social communication questionnaire-current and social responsiveness scale as teacher-report screening tools for autism spectrum disorders. *Journal of autism and developmental disorders*. 2012 Aug 1;42(8):1705-16.
14. Jordan R. Managing autism and Asperger's syndrome in current educational provision. *Pediatric rehabilitation*. 2005 Apr 1;8(2):104-12.
15. Khan MA. Country Report: Pakistan: Pakistan Country Report? *Autism*. In: Final report of the... Asia-Pacific International Seminar on Education for Individuals with Special Needs 2009 Dec (Vol. 29, pp. 83-88). 16. Imran N, Chaudry MR, Azeem MW, Bhatti MR, Choudhary ZI, Cheema MA. A survey of Autism knowledge and attitudes among the healthcare professionals in Lahore, Pakistan. *BMC pediatrics*. 2011 Dec;11(1):107.
16. Shetty A, Rai BS. Awareness and Knowledge of Autism Spectrum Disorders among Primary School Teachers in India. *International Journal of Health Sciences and Research (IJHSR)*. 2014;4(4):80-5.
17. Arif MM, Niazy A, Hassan B, Ahmed F. Awareness of autism in primary school teachers. *Autism research and treatment*. 2013;2013.
18. Haimour AI, Obaidat YF. School teachers' knowledge about autism in Saudi Arabia. *World Journal of Education*. 2013 Sep 1;3(5):45.
19. 20. Brown R, Hewstone M. An integrative theory of intergroup contact. *Advances in experimental social psychology*. 2005 Dec 31;37:255-343.
20. 21. Furnham A, Buck C. A comparison of lay-beliefs about autism and obsessive-compulsive disorder. *International Journal of Social Psychiatry*. 2003 Dec;49(4):287-307.
21. 22. Mattila ML, Jussila K, Kuusikko S, Kielinen M, Linna SL, Ebeling H, Bloigu R, Joskitt L, Pauls D, Moilanen I. When does the Autism Spectrum Screening Questionnaire (ASSQ) predict autism spectrum disorders in primary school-aged children? *European child & adolescent psychiatry*. 2009 Aug 1;18(8):499-509.
22. 23. Luleci NE, Hidioglu S, Karavus M, Karavus A, Sanver FF, Ozgur F, Celik M, Celik SC. The pharmacists' awareness, knowledge and attitude about childhood autism in Istanbul. *International journal of clinical pharmacy*. 2016 Dec 1;38(6):1477-82.
23. 24. Divan G, Vajaratkar V, Desai MU, Strik-Lievers L, Patel V. Challenges, coping strategies, and unmet needs of families with a child with autism spectrum disorder in Goa, India. *Autism Research*. 2012 Jun 1;5(3):190-200.
24. 25. Al-Sharbaty MM, Al-Farsi YM, Ouhtit A, Waly MI, Al-Shafae M, Al-Farsi O, Al-Khaduri M, Al-Said MF, Al-Adawi S. Awareness about autism among school teachers in Oman: A cross-sectional study. *Autism*. 2015 Jan;19(1):6-13.
25. 26. Cohen DJ. Diagnosis and classification of autism and related conditions: Consensus and issues. *Handbook of autism and pervasive developmental disorders*. 1996:5-34.
26. 27. McPheeters ML, Warren Z, Sathe N, Bruzek JL, Krishnaswami S, Jerome RN, Veenstra-VanderWeele J. A systematic review of medical treatments for children with autism spectrum disorders. *Pediatrics*. 2011 May 1;127(5):e1312-21.
27. 28. Mavropoulou S, Padelidu S. Greek teachers' perceptions of autism and implications for educational practice: A preliminary analysis. *Autism*. 2000 Jun;4(2):173-83.
28. 29. Branch SP. Teaching students with autism: A resource guide for schools.